

A study on the impact of Brand Management among rural people with reference to Manjunaath polytube, Tiruchengode

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ABSTRACT: Brand management is one of the driving forces which enacts the rules and enforcements that has to be followed by the company or the product to communicate with the market standards. The objective of the study is to analyze the impact of brand management among rural areas which is effective to Manjunaath Polytube, Tiruchengode. The sample size utilized for this study is 370. Descriptive research method and Convenience sampling techniques were used for the study. Data analysis has been done through percentage analysis, chi-square, correlation analysis. It is found that there is significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and to understand the brand awareness among the customers. It is suggested that the company should make aware about its range of prices to the customers to select the right products. There must be value for money for the brand to obtain positive perception towards the brand. It is concluded that when it extends its services and offer wide range of products in an excellent performance, its brand would be remains in the minds of customers and in the industry.

KEY WORDS: Brand management, Customer, Customer relationship, Products and Pricings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Brand image is the design and implementation of the rules that supports the company or the product for the market communications. This includes dictating boundaries on advertising, language, tone, and cadence of communication with the customers. Branding is very important for every business because it makes the product or the company unique from its competitors. It also plays a vital role in building the trust of the customers and makes them emotionally connected to the product. The main aim of the brand management is to create strong and positive reputation to the brand which implies on the increased market for the product.

BRAND MANAGEMENT - IMPORTANCE

When a company moves on with a strategy which is flexible and more useful, then that strategy would be very helpful to build a positive brand impression. However, the importance of strategic brands management is reflected in the following points:

- Increased customer satisfaction and customer retention to the company or the brand with trust.
- Better engagement of employees in achieving the company's objective
- Employees feel more closed to the company.
- Brand perception gets improved, and selling power strengthens up.
- Allows the company to have an impactful marketing communication.
- Increase customer responses and trade cooperation.
- It promotes licensing opportunities.

INDUSTRY PROFILE

As the manufacturing sector is blooming in India there is a high demand for the PVC pipe in the market condition. The enhanced and developed agriculture sector and the governments step towards the construction field had made the PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride) to the next level in Indian market. The major players of this sector with the greatest capitalization in this sector had an increased profit percentage of 3 to 11 year on year for the past two years. The major players operating in the India PVC pipes includes Finolex diligence limited, Ori-Plast limited, Apollo pipes, Prince pipes, etc.

COMPANY PROFILE

Manjunaath Polytube has plants located at now Animoor, Tiruchengode in Tamil Nadu. They have the largest manufacturing unit at a single location under one roof in Namakkal district at Tamil Nadu. Among the market leader in piping and related products segment under brand name of

Manjunaath Polytube PVC Pipes. The reputed and experienced Management Team of Manjunaath Polytube is led by young, energetic and dynamic leader Mr. Madheswaran. The main aim of the Manjunaath Polytube is to gain the trust from their customers as well as each and every employees working there and also with the investors about the brand. The plants use flexible manufacturing techniques, greener technologies and modern machinery.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Pfoertsch (2018), this analysis aims to examine the need of business □ to □ business companies for branding and analyzes the options for success by means of the stock performance. The paper consists of a qualitative and quantitative airman study and a quantitative main check. Long □ term branding strategies, brand performance and establishment's business performance are set up to be appreciatively identified with stock increase. The study has possible position □ and assiduity □ specific limitations. Managerially, the findings encourage enterprises to borrow a long □ term imprinting strategy, fastening not only on brand development.

Lee (2018), numerous companies are interested in the issue of how to develop strong brands. Although the brand operation system (BMS) within a establishment is veritably likely to have a positive impact on brand performance, there have been no empirical studies on the places of the BMS. In this paper, we develop a abstract model using the BMS and empirically examine its effect on brand performance. In particular, we compare how the BMS works as a interceding variable between request exposure and brand performance under B – B and B – C surroundings. The empirical results grounded on check data from 1000 brand directors (from 770 B – C and 230 B – B enterprises) show that enterprises enjoying a well-organized BMS dramatically enhance brand performance. This study also offers some counteraccusations and unborn exploration questions grounded on the current results.

Berthonet.al., (2019), Although an emotional body of literature has surfaced fastening on the critical conditioning involved in brand operation for larger associations with well-established brands and substantial marketing budgets, no exploration has been accepted to examine branding within small to medium- sized enterprises (SMEs). The present study thus seeks to assess the nature and compass of brand operation within an SME environment. Findings show

significant differences between small and large associations along 9 of the 10 brand operation confines reported in Keller's brand report card. also, different brand operation practices are associated with business performance in SMEs.

Mohammed (2019), the area of employer branding is an area of elevation in gift magnet. The main end of the paper is to explore the employer imprinting literature and its effect on attracting gift, hand performance, organizational culture and gaining competitive advantage in the request. Detailed literature review on this subject area is carried out on current practices of employer branding in gift magnet, impacts of employer branding practices. It was concluded that employer branding is the value proposition of workers and how the company can communicate this proposition to its prospective aspirants, which play in gift magnet and organizational success that helps the association in smoother reclamation process, hand satisfaction, hand retention and competitive advantage.

OBJECTIVES:

- To understand the brand awareness among the customers.
- To study on brand image among the customers.
- To evaluate the perceived quality towards the brand.
- To know the level of customer trust towards the brand.
- To obtain suggestions from the respondents to enhance brand management for the organization.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is the frame of exploration styles and ways chosen by an experimenter to conduct a study. The research design allows the researchers to understand the path towards which they have to travel to attain the desired result for the study. Creating an exploration content explains the type of exploration (experimental, check exploration, correlational, semi-experimental, review) and its sub-type (experimental design, exploration problem, descriptive case- study). Descriptive research design is used to analyze and interpret the study.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Sampling method or sampling technique is the process of studying the population by gathering information and analyzing that data. It is the basis of the data where the sample space is enormous.

There are several different sampling techniques available, and they can be subdivided into two groups. For this study, simple random sampling method had been employed.

SAMPLE UNIT

Sample unites are just the individual employees or customers of the population from which computations are done using the questionnaire. Sample units are always unique and does not over laps. The sample unit which has been chosen for this study is Triuchengode employees.

SAMPLE SIZE

Sample unit refers to the individual respondent or a set of respondents from where the information is analyzed and collected at different stages. The sample unit for this study is the employees of 370 employees Manjunaath Polytube, Tiruchengode.

STATISTICAL DESIGN

The collected data were analyzed with reference to each of the specific objectives of the study and the following statistical techniques were used in the study.

- Percentage analysis
- Chi-Square analysis
- Correlation analysis

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage methods are used to understand the information's or statistics of the collected data easily.

$$\frac{\text{Number of respondents}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} * 100$$

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

Chi-square is used to understand the relationship between the two variables. In this study it is used to understand the relationship between gender of the respondents and brand awareness.

$$x^2 = \frac{\sum(O - E)^2}{E}$$

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

In this study the correlation analysis had been done between gender of the respondents and perceived quality towards the brand. Correlation analysis has been done to understand the relationship between the two variables of the study, where is significant relationship or not.

$$r = \frac{\sum XY}{\sqrt{(\sum X^2)(\sum Y^2)}}$$

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

S.NO	Demographic Variable	Group	No. of respondents	Percentage of respondents
1.	Age	Below 25	45	12.2
		26-35	117	31.6
		36-45	127	34.3
		46-55	38	10.3
		Above 56	43	11.6
2.	Gender	Male	265	71.6
		Female	105	28.4
3.	Source for Brand knowledge	Newspaper	47	12.7
		Social media	135	36.5
		Website	113	30.5
		Word of mouth	36	9.7
		Television advertisements	39	10.5
4.	Years of dealing the brand	Below 1 years	65	17.6
		1-2years	80	21.6
		2-3 years	130	35.1
		3-4 years	50	13.5

		Above 4 years	45	12.2
5.	Brand preference is because	Brand image	83	22.4
		Quality	69	18.6
		Easy availability	144	38.9
		Fair price	44	11.9
		Brand reliable	30	8.1

INTERPRETATION

From the table the majority of the respondents were between the age group of 36-45 years, the majority of the respondents were male, the source for brand knowledge of majority of the respondents were social media, the years of dealing the brand of majority of the respondents were between 2-3 years, the majority of the respondents brand preference is because of the easy availability of the product.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS AND BRAND AWARENESS AMONG THE CUSTOMERS

Null hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and brand awareness among the customers.

Alternative hypothesis (H₁):

There is significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and brand awareness among the customers.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	96.416 ^a	13	.000
Likelihood Ratio	112.884	13	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	41.874	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	370		

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	96.416 ^a	13	.000
Likelihood Ratio	112.884	13	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	41.874	1	.000
a. 8 cells (28.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .85.			

INTERPRETATION:

As per the above table, it is inferred that the P value is 0.000; it is significant to 5% (0.05) significant level. The minimum expected count is 0.85. Thus, alternative hypothesis is accepted and it is found that there is some significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and brand awareness among the customers.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS AND PERCEIVED QUALITY TOWARDS THE BRAND

		GENDER	PERCEIVED QUALITY
GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS	Pearson Correlation	1	.102
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.050
	N	370	370
PERCEIVED QUALITY TOWARDS THE BRAND	Pearson Correlation	.102	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.050	
	N	370	370

INTERPRETATION:

The Above table indicates that out of 370 respondents, co-efficient of correlation between the age of the respondents and perceived quality towards the brand .is 0.102. It is below 1. So, there is positive relationship between age of the respondents and perceived quality towards the brand.

V. FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

FINDINGS

- 71.6% of the respondents are male.
- 34.3% of the respondents are in the age group of 36-45 years.
- 36.5% of the respondents said that social media as their source of knowing the brand.
- 35.1% of the respondents said that 2-3 years as they deal with the brand.
- 38.9% of the respondents said that easy availability as the reason for prefer the brand.
- There is some significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and brand awareness among the customers.

- There is positive relationship between age of the respondents and perceived quality towards the brand.

SUGGESTIONS

- The company must spread about its brand through various channels like newspaper, social media, website, positive word of mouth and television advertisements.
- The company has to maintain always brand image towards the concern. It must maintain the standard quality in its products.
- It must take all the efforts to avail its brand in all the outlet to reach the wider customers.
- The company has to fix the price in affordable manner to suit all sorts of

customers. It must maintain the reliability in its transactions and brand performance.

- The company has to make familiarize its offering range of products to its customers and it must show its uniqueness in its brand performance.
- The company should make aware about its range of prices to the customers to select the right products.
- There must be superiority in the brand than other brand in the market. There must be value for money for the brand to obtain positive perception towards the brand.
- The company should take all the efforts to resolve the customers complaints promptly to have good customer relationship.

CONCLUSION

Branding is one of the very important techniques to promote the business to the next step. It can also help make client fidelity and emotionally connect with the company. Branding can be complex, but it's essential to understand the basics before starting a brand strategy. The thing of brand operation is to produce a robust and positive character for a brand that will affect in increased deals and request share. Companies need to understand the different aspects of brand operation to produce a strong brand identity. Brand operation

can also help a company to charge a decoration price for its products or services.

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